

REHOUSE

ACCELERATING THE EUROPEAN
RENOVATION RATE

The focus of the REHOUSE project is to increase the scope and productivity of the renovation process, the improvement of comfort and satisfaction of the building inhabitants and users, and the increased use of integrated solutions for the decentralised generation of renewable energy.

Renovation packagEs for HOListic improvement of EU's bUILDINGS Efficiency, maximizing RESgeneration and cost-effectiveness

25 Partners
from 8 countries

Duration:
10/2022 – 09/2026

EU-funding:
10 Mio. €

Overview of REHOUSE Renovation Packages

Eight renovation packages will be deployed across the demo sites. The goal of the project is to make the renovation packages market-ready by demonstrating them across a variety of environments. By the end of the project the renovation packages will have a technology-readiness-level of seven or more.

Multi-source heat pump

Adaptable/dynamic
building envelope

SmartWall

Centralised Holistic
H&C Renovation Kit

Multipurpose façade
with bio-based insulation
and BIPV

PanoRen

Activated cellulose
thermal insulation

Intelligent window
system

Renovation solutions will be deployed across four demo sites

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REHOUSE PROJECT PARTNERS

CERTH
CENTRE FOR RESEARCH & TECHNOLOGY HELLAS

ΔΗΜΟΚΡΙΤΕΙΟ ΠΑΝΕΠΙΣΤΗΜΙΟ ΘΡΑΚΗΣ
DEMOCRITUS UNIVERSITY OF THRACE

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